

31 March 2026

EGEAN Stakeholder Mapping Report

(initial version)

SAEGE report

for the European Commission, the Public and those interested in the EGEAN

Funded by the European Union

Executive Summary

This document presents the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) Et Alia Advisory Network (EGEAN) mapping. It identifies and categorises organisations that may be relevant to the European and international **ethics advisory ecosystem for science and new technologies**. The mapping sets out the scope of actors included, the inclusion and exclusion criteria applied, and the methods used to identify relevant organisations. It also provides a working list of relevant entities identified through the mapping process. The document serves as a practical reference to support ongoing EGEAN engagement and will be updated periodically to reflect changes in the ethics advisory landscape and the scope of the EGE's work.

Document Information

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Project name	Support for the activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies
Project acronym	SAEGE
Project number	101256865
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Last update	31 March 2026

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List of acronyms

- **AE** Academia Europaea
- **ALLEA** All European Academies
- **ART** Antiretroviral therapy
- **CSO** Civil society organisation
- **EGE** European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
- **EGEAN** EGE Et Alia Advisory Network
- **EUREC** European Network of Research Ethics Committees
- **NEC Forum** National Ethics Councils Forum
- **NGO** Non-governmental organisation
- **REC** Research ethics committee
- **SAEGE** Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies
- **SAPEA** Scientific Advice for Policy by European Academies
- **YASAS** Young Academies Science Advice Structure

The EGEAN – An introduction

The main output of this report is a compilation of **115 organisations** that can form the starting point of a network called the European Group of Ethics *Et Alia* Advisory Network, the EGEAN.

The name stems from a 2025 funding call from the European Commission, which asked, amongst other things, for the following:

- “Strengthen the links between European science and ethics organisations, including a diverse range of experts.”
- “An open and inclusive approach will be used... to increase ... the excellence of the expertise provided.”
- “Increase awareness of the significance of ethics advice and ensure outreach to larger audiences.”
- “Reinforce ... the ethics advice network comprising the EGE, the Beneficiary [SAEGE], and the other actors—such as national and international ethics advisory bodies—that make up the EGE Et Alia Advisory Network (hereafter: the EGEAN)”.

In brief, the call asks for, excellent expertise from a diverse range of experts, assembled through an open and inclusive approach, that links science and ethics, increases awareness of ethics advice and reaches larger audiences, all with the support of the EGEAN.

To increase the excellence of expertise available in the ethics advisory ecosystem, in an open and inclusive manner, includes avoiding “**meritocratic hubris**” (Sandel 2020: 14). Michael Sandel, one of the world's most influential living political philosophers, has noted that: “history shows little connection between prestigious academic credentials and either practical wisdom or an instinct for the common good in the here and now” (Sandel 2020: 90, see also David Archard (2011)).

If ethics advice is based on:

“single-interest forms of ethics expertise, [it] ... can uphold systematic injustices, weaken democratic rights and dignity, diminish fair processes, institutions and outcomes, and lead to a decline of public reasoning and deliberation” (Pykett et al 2026).

Hence, ethics advice is only as strong as the expertise and experiences it can draw from.

This report focuses on the first step to addressing this problem, namely the creation of the European Group of Ethics *Et Alia* Advisory Network, the EGEAN. It is the task of SAEGE (a project funded to support the European Group on Ethics) to try and establish this network with the aim of procuring access to a wide spectrum of national and international actors from the ethics advisory ecosystem.

In a second step, an **Inclusion Plan** aims to ensure that diverse perspectives are integrated into ethical discussions, addressing as yet underrepresented disciplines, regions, and perspectives. In particular, measures will be implemented to ensure that the EGE, SAEGE and the EGEAN can access the **lived experiences and expertise** of those who might be affected by science and technology developments. Thus, the mapping that is described in this report leads to the **Starter EGEAN** and only when it is combined with the actions from the Inclusion plan, will an **Advanced EGEAN** become possible (see also figure below).

How the EGEAN will be built

The early vision for the EGEAN, as set by a call from the European Commission, is to provide diverse ethics advisory expertise, via SAEGE, to support the EGE. Two challenges present themselves: first, how can a diverse network be created; and second, how can it be sustained.

This section is about the first challenge. It includes a description of how organisations were identified and why they were included in the first list of potential EGEAN members.

The ethics-policy advisory ecosystem – A mapping exercise

Pykett et al. (2026) describe an “**ethics-policy advisory ecosystem**” as a network of actors and institutions that provide ethical reflection and normative judgement for policy across different levels.

The ecosystem metaphor suggests that ethics advice is shaped by its institutional and political context rather than delivered by a single authority or form of expertise. Importantly, though, ethics advice should be guided by stable values, seeking a balance between flexibility and integrity to be trustworthy. Understanding ethics advice in this way supports a multi-actor and multi-level approach to the mapping exercise for this report.

Which expertise is relevant

For the purpose of initial mapping and to achieve consistency, identification of potential EGEAN members **focused primarily on organisations, networks, and institutional bodies** active in ethics advice, including academies, ethics councils, professional associations, ethics networks, civil society organisations (CSOs) and non-government organisations (NGOs). This approach circumvents personal data protection issues that would surface if we identified named individuals for the Starter EGEAN.

However, in the long run, the EGEAN is conceived as a **people-centred network**. While organisations provide an essential entry point for mapping the ecosystem, SAEGE recognises that effective network-building depends on engaging *individuals*, i.e., the ethics advisors, practitioners, researchers, policy experts, and experiential experts who generate, interpret, and apply ethical insight in practice.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

To identify relevant organisations, **inclusion and exclusion criteria** for the EGEAN mapping exercise were formulated by the SAEGE team.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion
I1) Organisations	E1) Individual ethics advisors
I2) Regularly involved in providing policy advice	E2) Lack of demonstrable expertise in policy advice
I3) Representing communities or groups who might experience negative consequences from science and new technology developments	E3) Temporary, unstable, or inactive entities with – at best – only very occasional, e.g. one-off, involvement in policy advice
	E4) Those involved in policy advice with partisan mandates, e.g. lobbyists with commercial interests
	E5) Organisations that do not operate or communicate in English
	E6) Standalone institutional ethics committees or similar standalone entities within organisations
	E7) Policy advice organisations that focus exclusively on non-European domestic issues

In line with the funding call's focus on securing access to a 'diverse range of experts', the main aim of the EGEAN mapping exercise was to identify organisations that provide advice to public authorities, research institutions, professional bodies, or governance units on matters related to science or emerging technologies where they intersect with ethics (criteria I1 and I2). Identifying such organisations could lead to a network that can mobilise actors who actively contribute to ethical reflection and guidance within science and technology advisory ecosystems.

A secondary main aim, focused on the 'open and inclusive approach' from the call text, tried to identify organisations that represent communities or groups who are likely to experience ethical consequences from science and new technologies (criterion I3). This inclusion criterion aims to ensure that **ethical reflection remains socially grounded and inclusively informed**.

Exclusion criteria were more numerous than inclusion criteria. Excluded were those organisations that did **not show enough relevance or demonstrable expertise** (E2). Entities whose primary mission did not intersect with ethics advice, the governance of science and technology, or public values in policymaking, or who did not have identifiable expertise, mandate, or sustained activity (e.g., through publishing, advising, networking, regulating, researching, or representing communities) were excluded. This ensures that the network includes only actors who can meaningfully contribute to ethics-oriented discussions within the advisory ecosystem.

Likewise, **temporary, unstable, or inactive** organisations were excluded (E3), such as temporary projects, one-off campaigns, and organisations that have not been active within the past two years. These actors are unlikely to

support sustained engagement or contribute to long-term network development.

E4 excluded those organisations with **potential conflicts of interest or partisan mandates**. Entities that are heavily reliant on corporate funding or whose activities are strongly driven by commercial interests, or that have explicit partisan mandates, were excluded. This helps to ensure that the network’s discussions are not unduly influenced by commercial or partisan agendas.

A more practical exclusion criterion, E5, was organisations **that do not operate or communicate in English**. Entities that cannot be reliably identified or contacted using English were excluded because English will be the primary language for network activities and communications.

Standalone institutional ethics committees (e.g. single-hospital or single-university research ethics committees) were excluded (E6) unless they operated a policy-relevant network or have a mandate to engage in ethics advice beyond their host institution. Such bodies typically focus on internal review, teaching, or research rather than system-level ethics advice or policy engagement. In addition, relevant academic and research ethics networks were already included in the EGEAN through organisations found with I2, and including individual committees would risk duplication without adding commensurate advisory value.

Finally, E7, organisations **focused exclusively on non-European domestic issues** were excluded. While the EGEAN is meant to be globally oriented and it is clear that ethical challenges cross borders and often require global

solutions, actors whose work is limited *solely* to non-global domestic issues outside of Europe were excluded.

The search

Using the inclusion and exclusion criteria, three steps were undertaken to arrive at the current number of 115 organisations that could form the Starter EGEAN: initial mapping, systematic search, and snowball search.

Initial mapping

The **initial mapping** identified organisations that were already known to the SAEGE team, as well as those documented in prior mapping exercises in ethics and science-for-policy projects accessible to the team. The former included:

1. the members of networks with budgeted collaboration in SAEGE (All European Academies (ALLEA), Academia Europaea, and the Young Academies Science Advice Structure (YASAS)),
2. bodies associated with the European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC), the host of SAEGE, and
3. organisations that have participated in EU-funded projects related to ethics in science and new technologies.

Point 3 focused on a preliminary mapping of science-for-policy organisations undertaken within Scientific Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA). [SAPEA](#) is a consortium of approximately 120 European academies and societies that provides independent, evidence-based reports to inform EU policy. The SAPEA search had combined a targeted LinkedIn search for science-policy officers and a structured Google scan using search strings pairing “science for policy” with individual countries.

Systematic search

The initial mapping was followed by a **systematic search**. We used the [Search Engine Scraper](#), as implemented in a study on research ethics and integrity guidelines (Hastings et al., 2025), to identify additional organisations not yet captured. Searches were conducted via the DuckDuckGo search engine, with the top 300 results per country scraped and screened against the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined above.

The search strings used were pilot-tested. They were designed to capture bodies operating at the intersection of ethics, science, technology, and policy, irrespective of organisational form or sector. While the scraper tool allows for country-level searches – for example, applying a single search string across all EU Member States – this approach yielded mostly duplicate results during pilot-testing. To maximise coverage and minimise duplication, twelve search strings were developed, split between Europe-focused and international-focused queries. Boolean operators could not be used, as they were not supported by the scraper tool during pilot testing. The search strings used were as follows:

- “science technology ethics policy forum Europe”

- “science technology ethics policy council Europe”
- “science technology ethics policy committee Europe”
- “science technology ethics policy association Europe”
- “science technology ethics policy organisation Europe”
- “science technology ethics policy network Europe”
- “science technology ethics policy forum international”
- “science technology ethics policy council international”
- “science technology ethics policy committee international”
- “science technology ethics policy association international”
- “science technology ethics policy organisation international”
- “science technology ethics policy network international”

In total, 3,326 results were screened across all searches. 565 entries were identified as duplicates and removed from further consideration. 2,733 entries were excluded based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria, leaving 28 organisations for the EGEAN map.

The 2,733 exclusions were distributed as follows:

Exclusion criterion	Number
Lack of relevance or demonstrable expertise	2,663
Temporary, inactive, or non-institutional entities	24
Standalone institutional ethics committees or similar	20
Organisations with an exclusive focus on non-European domestic issues	20
Potential conflicts of interest or partisan mandates	6
Total	2,733

Snowball search

A snowball search was conducted alongside the systematic search by inviting targeted input from networks with budgeted collaboration under SAEGE – namely Academia Europaea (AE), Young Academies Science Advice Structure (YASAS), and All European Academies (ALLEA), as well as from the EGE Secretariat and the National Ethics Councils (NEC) Forum. Proposed additions were subsequently cross-checked against the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and duplicates were removed.

The categorisation

The above search identified 115 organisations, see Annex 1. To support the strategic planning for network engagement and seek to establish balance within the EGEAN, the organisations were categorized according to:

- Entity type
- Main topical area
- Main geographic scope

Entity type

The entity type distribution after the above-described searches is as follows:

Main topical area

We also divided the identified organisations according to specialist areas of expertise as follows.

Category	Example of potential policy input
Governance ethics	Research ethics guidelines for research funders
Bioethics	Policies on physician-assisted suicide
Environmental ethics	Using the precautionary principle in agricultural policies
AI and emerging technologies ethics	How to ensure non-discrimination rights

Organisations that had several foci for their main work were listed with the prime focus, whilst some organisations cover all topics.

Main geographic scope

The main geographic scope is predominantly international or European given the exclusion criterion of a focus on non-European domestic issues. The exact distribution is as follows:

African 4; Asian 7; Australasian 2; European 40, Latin American 3; North American 4 and International 55.

If one maps the administrative or legal headquarters of all 115 organisations, one can see the following geographic spread (bearing in mind that some entities do not have headquarters and a very small number have up to three).

EGEAN Potential Members Headquarters

The above has described how the list for the Starter EGEAN was systematically built and now includes a significant number of organisations from the ethics advisory ecosystem for science and new technologies.

Inclusion criterion I3 had generated almost no additions to the EGEAN, namely: "Representing communities or groups who might experience negative consequences from science and new technology developments." This will be remedied through inclusion measures to be outlined in the Inclusion Plan, prior to having an Advanced EGEAN membership list.

The **Inclusion Plan** will contribute two key elements to the EGEAN. First, it will contribute a list of organisations that promote the interests of groups whose perspectives might differ from the general population, e.g., disabled people, refugees, survivors of violence, LGBTQ+ groups, people living in serious poverty, the unemployed etc. Second, it will contribute a sample moral framework and implementation guide for how the lived experiences of marginalized groups can be analysed and incorporated into policy advice. Once this work has been completed, the Advanced EGEAN can be built.

The EGEAN list will be a **living document**, updated annually; in this way, the EGEAN will remain responsive to emerging ethical issues and new actors within the system.

Network of networks

Within the 115 organisations that our search identified as belonging to the ethics advisory ecosystem for science and new technologies, some represent large networks themselves. Four of those networks are already committed to the EGEAN, namely:

- The **National Ethics Council Forum**, i.e. all national ethics committee from the European Member States and the United Kingdom (44 organisations).
- The 27 organisations of **EUREC**, a network of national research ethics committees in Europe.
- The 59 European Academies which form the **ALLEA** network.
- The 22 Academies that form the Young Academies Science Advice Structure (**YASAS**).

Likewise, **Academia Europaea** is committed to the EGEAN, while not being a network of networks, but a group of more than 5,500 elected members, including over 80 Nobel laureates.

This gives an idea of the people power behind the 115 organisations that may form the Starter EGEAN.

Before we explain how the organisations will be contacted and what initial ideas are for running the EGEAN, we come back to the second challenge: how can a network of this size be sustained in the longer term.

Benefits for members

As noted earlier, two challenges present themselves in the context of building the EGEAN: first, how can a diverse network be created and second, how can it be sustained. This section is a starter discussion for the latter point.

“Organisational networks are multilayered and **evolve over time**” (Piccolo et al 2022 – emphasis added). One cannot, as an individual player in the ethics advisory ecosystem (in this case the individual player SAEGE), force the success of a network overnight. Whether a network succeeds depends crucially on whether there is something in it for the members. It is therefore important that invitations to potential members are only extended when it is clear what the benefits will be. Hence, the following timeline is envisaged:

At the moment, the following benefits are envisaged for EGEAN members (while further ones may be developed over time):

- **Topical workshops and roundtables** on key ethics themes, chaired – where possible – by members of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) and involving national ethics councils, European Commission representatives, and other stakeholders.
- **Skills development and best-practice exchange** through briefings and learning sessions, online and in person. For instance, skills development on how policy impact can be achieved.
- **A regular newsletter** to share updates and disseminate the work of the EGE.
- **Peer-to-peer collaboration tools**, including a moderated listserver and an expert database supporting direct connections.
- **Access to a ‘Red Button’ early alert mechanism** for members to flag urgent or emerging ethics issues.
- **A flagship event at the project end** to consolidate achievements and discuss pathways for future development.

Given that the first entry, topical workshops and roundtables, are well suited to increase early interest of the EGEAN, they are described in more detail below. For all other entries in the list, it is envisaged that the EGEAN is operational and members can then co-develop further activities with SAEGE.

SAEGE is committed, by grant agreement, to organising events as follows:

“Skills development and sharing of best practice. SAEGE will organise briefings and other opportunities for exchange (which may be delivered online and in person) on topics related to gathering and synthesising evidence for policy advice, bringing together EGE members and other experts in every part of the process, and drawing on the European science advice community via the project staff’s close connections. Leading participation of EGE members will be prioritised in these activities, thereby also contributing to O5 (strengthening the impact of the EGE’s work).”

Once invitations have been issued to potential members (by 31 May 2026), a **first webinar series on ethics advice for policy** will be launched. Each webinar in a series will discuss different aspects of how ethics advice should work, and which challenges are involved. According to the current planning, each webinar should:

- include an external speaker and
- an EGE speaker as respondent or co-host;
- be short and accessible, i.e. 45 minutes, or up to 60 minutes maximum;
- be time zone friendly, i.e. slots will not exclude some regions permanently;
- have an informal, roundtable feel where members can express views and engage with the external speaker and the EGE;

- be recorded for future reference and/or sharing on the SAEGE YouTube channel.

In addition to providing an opportunity for exchanges on the topic of ethics advice for policy, the webinars aim to:

- raise and discuss important issues that the EGE and SAEGE can take on board in their work;
- promote the EGE among key stakeholders;
- alert people to the existence of SAEGE.

Whilst this gives an example of initial ideas, it is essential that the network develops with input from all members. How members will be contacted is described in the next section.

Outreach

We now have a potential Starter EGEAN of 115 possible members, which is likely to be expanded with more entities following the work done for the Inclusion Plan. Yet, the development of an *active* EGEAN is not easily accomplished.

Our preference for moving from the drawing board to an active EGEAN is as follows:

- It is essential that the EGEAN is part of a brand and that all members who are invited to participate can inform themselves about the EGE and SAEGE on a well-designed website.
- The website is also necessary to register interest in webinars. Without a branded website, it is therefore not possible to organise the first main activity of the EGEAN.

Once the website is available, the first event will be made public and thereafter organisations will be approached on an individual basis in one of two main ways. First, the **preferred option** is to invite an organisation to join the EGEAN via colleagues that are already known to them. It will be key to this approach that ALLEA, Academia Europaea, YASAS, EUREC, and the NEC Forum are already committed to the EGEAN and might act as spokespeople or intermediaries. Second, where the preferred option is not available, contact will be made through a tailored email sent by **a senior**

member of SAEGE. The exact details of reaching out to potential members will be agreed with the SAEGE Steering Committee.

The SAEGE Steering Committee and how it will help build the EGEAN

The SAEGE Steering Committee was established in January 2026 to guide the early development of the EGEAN. The committee is currently composed of representatives from ALLEA, Academia Europaea, YASAS, EUREC, and the NEC Forum.

As these organisations operate as **well-connected, pan-European networks**, their involvement provides a strong foundation for supporting the recruitment of EGEAN members and ensuring broad disciplinary, geographical, and professional representation. Their collective reach spans national ethics councils, academies of sciences and humanities, university networks, and research ethics committees, offering a unique gateway to Europe's diverse ethics and scientific communities.

The Steering Committee will play **a central role in shaping the strategic direction** of the EGEAN during its initial phase. It will support SAEGE in defining priorities for network expansion, identifying emerging expertise needs, and ensuring that stakeholder engagement remains inclusive and aligned with the project's objectives. The committee also serves as a key liaison connection to the wider ethics landscape, ensuring coherence and complementarity across the EGEAN's activities.

Quarterly meetings will allow the committee to review progress, assess whether recruitment and engagement mechanisms are working effectively, and adjust strategic focus where needed. Through their advisory function, members will help ensure that the EGEAN becomes a robust, dynamic, and representative advisory network capable of providing expert input into SAEGE's early-alert mechanism, ethical analyses, and policy-relevant work for the EGE.

In the longer term, the Steering Committee is also expected to support the organisation of knowledge-exchange and capacity-building activities for EGEAN members. These may include, as noted earlier:

- Topical workshops and roundtables on key ethics themes,
- Skills-development sessions and best-practice exchanges, delivered online or in person, focusing on practical competencies such as how to achieve policy impact, strengthen ethics review processes, or integrate insights from emerging technologies.

Through these activities, the Steering Committee will contribute directly to the professional development of EGEAN members and to the strengthening of the broader European ethics advisory ecosystem.

Conclusion

Europe has hitherto lacked a comprehensive ethics advice system, and this report describes the first step towards closing this gap.

In a mapping exercise, **115 organisations** were identified that can form the starting point of a network called the European Group of Ethics *Et Alia* Advisory Network, the **EGEAN**.

As single-interest forms of ethics expertise or meritocratic hubris cannot address systematic injustices or strengthen democratic processes, this first step will be enhanced with an Inclusion Plan. The Plan will ensure that the EGEAN can integrate diverse perspectives into ethical discussions.

The SAEGE Steering Committee, consisting of well-connected, pan-European networks, aims to ensure that the early outreach activities for the EGEAN will be successful.

Potential benefits to members include:

The SAEGE team are committed to creating an effective, engaged EGEAN so that the European ethics-policy advisory ecosystem can thrive and contribute its part to upholding the core values of the EU: respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and human rights—including minority rights—ensuring a society characterized by pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, and justice (European Parliament 2021).

Annex 1 – Organisations identified through search

- Academia Europaea, <https://www.ae-info.org/>
- 4TU Centre for Ethics and Technology, <https://www.4tu.nl/ethics/>
- Active Citizenship Network, <https://www.interestgroup.activecitizenship.net/about-us.html>
- Africa Bioethics Network (ABN), <https://africabioethicsnetwork.org/About%20ABN.html>
- African Union Ethics Office, <https://au.int/en/ethics>
- African Union High-Level Panel on Emerging Technologies, <https://www.nepad.org/microsite/african-union-high-level-panel-emerging-technologies-apat>
- AI Safety Asia, <https://www.aisafety.asia/what-we-do>
- AI4People Institute, <https://ai4people.org/ai4people-institute/>
- AlgorithmWatch, <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/>
- American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), <https://www.aaas.org/mission>
- American Society for Bioethics & Humanities, <https://asbh.org/>
- Asian Bioethics Network, <https://www.bioethics-singapore.gov.sg/asian-bioethics-network/>
- Asian Civil Society Research Network, <https://asiancivilsociety.com/>
- Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences (AAPS), <https://participatorysciences.org/>
- Association of AI Ethicists, <https://ethicists.ai/about-us/>
- Australasian Association of Bioethics and Health Law, <https://aabhl.org/>
- Business Council for Ethics of AI, <https://www.unesco.org/en/artificial-intelligence/business-council>
- Canadian Bioethics Society, <https://cbs-scb.ca/>
- Carnegie Council for Ethics in International Affairs, <https://carnegiecouncil.org/>
- Center for Democracy and Technology, <https://cdt.org/who-we-are/>
- Center for Environmental and Technology Ethics, <https://cetep.eu/>
- Center for Environmental Ethics and Law, <https://www.environmentalethicsandlaw.org/>
- Center for Ethics of Technology, <https://ethicstech.eu/en/>
- Center for Humane Technology, <https://www.humanetech.com/>
- CESAER - Conference of European Schools for Advanced Engineering Education and Research, a non-profit association of universities of science and technology in Europe, <https://www.cesaer.org/>

- Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS), <https://cioms.ch/>
- Ethical Data Initiative, <https://tumthinktank.de/en/project/ethical-data-intiative/>
- Ethics, Evidence, and Policy Network, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/15790031/>
- EticALIA (LAC AI Ethics Consortium), <https://eticalia.uff.br/>
- EU4Health Civil Society Alliance, <https://eu4health.eu/about-us/>
- Eubios Ethics Institute, <https://eubios.info/>
- European Academies' Science Advisory Council (EASAC), <https://easac.eu/>
- European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST), <https://easst.net/about-easst/>
- European Association of Centres of Medical Ethics, <https://eacmeweb.com/>
- European Business Ethics Network, <https://eben-net.online/>
- European Citizen Science Association, <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>
- European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA), <https://allea.org/>
- European Federation of Data Protection Officers, <https://www.efdpo.eu/>
- European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA), <https://www.efpia.eu/>
- European Medical Association (EMA), <https://emanet.org/>
- European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC), <https://eurecnet.eu/about-eurec/about-us/>
- European Patient Advocacy Institute, <https://www.patientadvocacy.eu/about-us/>
- European Patients Forum, <https://www.eu-patient.eu/members/>
- European Science Advisors Forum (ESAF), <https://esaforum.eu/>
- European Society for Philosophy of Medicine and Healthcare, <https://www.espmh.org/about/>
- European Society of Human Genetics, <https://www.eshg.org/pec>
- EURORDIS ePAGs, <https://www.eurordis.org/our-priorities/european-reference-networks/epag/>
- Fair Tech Policy Lab, <https://www.fairtechpolicylab.org/>
- Federation of European Academies of Medicine (FEAM), <https://www.feam.eu/>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), <https://www.fao.org/home/en>
- Food Ethics Council, <https://www.foodethicscouncil.org/>
- Forum for Ethical Review Committees in the Asian and Western Pacific Region (FERCAP), <https://www.sidcer-fercap.org/pages/whats-fercap.php>
- Future of Privacy Forum, <https://fpf.org/about/>
- Global Applied Ethics Institute, <https://gaei.org/>
- Global Ecological Integrity Group, <https://www.globalecointegrity.org/>
- Global Forum on Bioethics in Research, <https://www.gfbr.global/>
- Global Health Bioethics Network, <https://globalhealthbioethics.tghn.org/>
- Globethics, <https://globethics.net/about-us>

- Human Genome Organization (HUGO), <https://www.hugo-international.org/about-us/>
- IBERO-American Bioethics Network, <https://iabioethics.world/ibero-american-1>
- Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), <https://www.ieee.org/>
- InterAcademy Partnership, <https://www.interacademies.org/>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), <https://unfoundation.org/>
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), <https://www.ipbes.net/>
- International Alliance of Patients' Organizations, <https://www.iapo.org.uk/about-us>
- International Association for Environmental Philosophy, <https://environmentalphilosophy.org/>
- International Association for Promoting Geoethics, <https://www.geoethics.org/>
- International Association for Safe & Ethical AI (IASEAI), <https://www.iaseai.org/>
- International Association of Bioethics, <https://iabioethics.world/>
- International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), <https://iiasa.ac.at/>
- International Network on Feminist Approaches to Bioethics, <https://www.fabnet.org/>
- International Neuroethics Society, <https://neuroethicsociety.org/>
- International Science Council, <https://council.science/>
- International Society for Environmental Ethics, <https://iseethics.wordpress.com/history/>
- International Society for Ethics and Information Technology, <https://inseit.eu/>
- International Society for Ethics in Science and Technology (ISEST), <https://www.linkedin.com/company/iseest/posts>
- International Society for Stem Cell Research, <https://www.isscr.org/>
- International Society of Bioethics (SIBI), <https://sibi.org/sibi/>
- Markkula Center for Applied Ethics, <https://www.scu.edu/institute-for-technology-ethics-and-culture/>
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- NeuroGene, <https://neurogene.org/about/>
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- Technology, Knowledge & Society Research Network, <https://techandsoc.com/>
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